

SELF-DETERMINATION AND SECESSION AMONG THE INDIGENOUS PEOPLE OF SOUTH-EAST,
NIGERIA

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Abstract

Self-Determination and Secession movements have become a recurrent clamour in recent years. States in Africa and beyond have all had their fair share of agitations and Nigeria is not exempted. What is responsible for this new trend? And how have such movements impacted on peace and stability of the parent states? In carrying out this investigation, the study focused on the South-East region of Nigeria as the region has been at the forefront of the clamour for secession in recent years under the umbrella of Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB). The study purposively selected Abia, Anambra, and the Imo States as study areas because there appears to be a high prevalence of Biafran agitations in these three states. The Human Needs Theory (HNT) by John Burton in 1990 was adopted in this study and an annexe-post-factor research design and descriptive survey design were utilized. A sample size of five hundred (500) respondents was drawn from the study population with the aid of Taro Yamane Formula. Questionnaire, Interviews and Observation were also used as an instrument for Data Collection. Tables, simple percentages and charts were used to present and analyse data emanating from the research questions. The hypotheses were tested with Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The findings revealed that the major factor contributing to self-determination and secession in the south-east is political and economic marginalization as well as infrastructural decay. Also, the study revealed that the agitations in the region have encouraged political apathy in the South-east and resentment towards the federal government and her umpires. The study, therefore, recommends amongst others that there is an urgent need to organize town hall meetings across the five states of the South-east to ascertain the remote concerns and yearnings of the people. Doing so will give the impression that the Nigerian government is willing and responsive to address clamours from the region and give a sense of belonging to the people of the Southeast.

Keyword: Self-Determination, Secession, Indigenous, South-East, and Nigeria.

I. Introduction

This pursuit for freedom by segments of a state, separatists or national liberation movements has often taken a turn to more violent means as they sometimes develop militant wings that repeatedly unleash attacks against the apparatus and citizens of the said state. According to Blackman (1998), throughout history the death and birth of states have been a bloody process, usually fueled by ethnic hatred and often entailing the commission of mass atrocities against vulnerable minority groups. In the same vein, Hosoe (2011) asserts that conflicts, including armed conflicts, is triggered either by the exercise of the right to self-determination or by efforts to resist it. Indeed, the result of such violent campaigns by the separatist groups has sometimes led to the downfall of existing regimes and the establishment of new governments or national entities. Hence, on several occasions, we have witnessed yesterday's freedom fighter or rebel leader become tomorrow's head of state. Examples abound such as that of the late Laurent Kabila of Congo who through his Alliance of Democratic Forces for the Liberation of Congo-Zaire (ADLF) ousted the leadership of Mobutu Sese Seko; and Meles

Zenawi of Ethiopia whose Tigray People's Liberation Front (TPLF) in alliance with the Ethiopian People's Revolutionary Democratic Front (EPRDF) overthrew the country's then military junta BBCNEWS (2005).

With regards to the Nigerian state, the country has had its fair share of self-determination agitations since it emerged as a nation. Nigeria has been struggling with the challenge of how to coalesce the numerous ethnic nationalities in the country into one united nation. The challenge of forging national consciousness and unity among the different ethnic nationalities have always been compounded by the inability of successive governments to frontally address the problems associated with citizenship, religion, ethnicity, inequality, resource distribution, native-settler dichotomy and development (Adangor, 2017). This negative fallout from the situation has not only promoted disunity and mistrust among Nigerians but has manifested in resentful dispositions towards the Nigerian state exhibited by nationalities that feel disadvantaged and aggrieved. To this end, separatist agitations which have remained a regular feature of Nigerian politics remain a veritable tool for the expression of discontent with the Nigerian state and a platform for demanding adequate political accommodation.

Currently, there appear to be separatist agitations in virtually every region of the country judging from the call for Oduduwa Republic (Yoruba Nation) in the South West region, the call for Arewa Republic in the North, the Niger Delta Republic in the South-South, and the Biafra Republic in the South-East, not to mention the several calls from various sections of the country for a sovereign national conference to decide if the federating units of the country still want to live together under one sovereign entity called Nigeria and if so under what arrangement?.

The South-East region which has been at the forefront of the separatist agitations in Nigeria reiterates their continued exclusion from the political and socio-economic mainstream of the country which has reinforced their clamour for secession from Nigeria. If marginalization constitutes the major reason posited by people of South-Eastern Nigeria on the need to secede, would secession provide the needed peace, stability and economic development they heartily wish for? This is the important question begging for answers and none of the reviewed literature has provided this critical answer.

It is a common assumption for social scientists that for a polity to prosper there must be stability. Desirable international norms such as stability and predictability are difficult to achieve when many nation-states are submerged in a crisis of secession. The potential for violent conflicts is usually high and the clamour for secession also picks when people begin to lose faith in their government.

Taking into account the plethora of separatist and national liberation movements that have existed and even now continue to escalate, and its implication on the peace and stability of the Nigerian State, it certainly would not be out of place to wonder if there exists a certain threshold upon which self-determination and secession is the recipe for peace and stability in a State. In other words, can secession guarantee lasting peace in a country? This study, therefore, takes a look at the concept of secession and the right to self-determination against the backdrop of peace. It is given the above that the following questions are deduced to guide the study. The burning questions of this research, therefore, are: What are the political, ethnic and socio-economic reasons for the movement for self-determination and secession in south-east Nigeria? And what are the impacts of the movement for self-determination and secession on the political stability of Nigeria? The above questions form the research questions for this study. These questions are important for many reasons, however, the most cardinal of them all is the universally held idea that all states need to maintain political stability for peace and progress.

For better understanding, a brief definition and history of the two major terms (self-determination and secession) driving this research is pertinent.

Self-Determination

The origin of self-determination can be traced back to the French Revolution of 1789. It was however in the 20th century that the concept gained real currency. In corroborating, the above, Kohn, (2016, p. 526) in Antidze (2016) observed that:

The concept of the right to self-determination can be found long before the creation of the UN. This concept firstly appeared in the Peace of Westphalia, and later at the end of the 18th century during the American and French revolutions...

The concept of 'self-determination' means different things to different people, consequently, several meanings have been attached to the concept. For Woodrow Wilson, the concept of 'self-determination' means government by consent (Taiwo, 2017). Scholars such as Zimuto(2015) support this conception of self-determination by arguing that self-determination must be understood as the right to democratic government. He is quoted as saying:

The new understanding of self-determination that has emerged may be restated as a right to self-determination that serves the well-being of groups who define themselves as a people by addressing the conditions under which they live and are governed through an ongoing process of negotiation of the terms on which they live with their neighbours.

The above line of reasoning suggests that Self-Determination is a human right that should be enjoyed by all peoples irrespective of race, ethnicity and culture.

Secession

Secession is concerned with a claim to statehood through breaking away from a sovereign state. Three notable forms of secessions exist namely; bilateral, de facto and unilateral or remedial secession. Bilateral secession occurs when a sovereign state consents or grants independence to a seceding entity through negotiation. An example of bilateral secession would be the secession of Montenegro from the state of Serbia and Montenegro. The secession of South Sudan from Sudan is another example of bilateral secession which was preceded by a referendum. De facto secession occurs when a seceding entity declares independence without any consent from the parent state. An example of de facto secession would be the de facto secession of Somaliland from Somalia (Zimuto, 2015). Remedial secession refers to secession motivated by gross human rights violations perpetrated by a state on its people (Adangor, 2017).

Conceptualization

Trends in Self-Determination Agitations in Nigeria

The attempt for Biafra secession from Nigeria in 1967 was not the first of its kind in Nigeria. The secession attempt itself was the culmination of the various contradictions within the Nigerian state. Various constitutions had been negotiated and adopted before 1966, but none addressed the fundamental social differences, political tensions, economic competition and ethnic imbalances that the Nigerian state had struggled with since amalgamation. Before the secession attempt by the Eastern Region that led to the war, the Hausa/Fulani, dominant in

the then Northern region, and the Yoruba, who dominated the then Western region, had all contemplated and sometimes threatened secession. Thus, Tamuno (1970) had traced the agitations for secession in the country to 1914. He noted that from Ahmadu Bello's (former premier of Northern Nigeria) account, the north would have preferred a separate political future, instead of being yoked with the south in what Bello termed "the mistake of 1914".

Towards the end of 1953, it was the turn of the Yoruba, in the west, to threaten to secede. This resulted from the contention over the status of Lagos (Awofeso, 2017). While the colonial authority and the rest of Nigeria wanted Lagos to remain a neutral territory as the federal capital, Chief Awolowo (a Nigerian Statesman) and his party wanted it to be administered as part of the western region. As the disagreement raged, Awolowo sent a strong-worded cable to the Secretary of State in which he claimed the freedom of the Western region "to decide whether or not they will remain in the proposed Nigerian Federation" (Tamuno, 1970). In the resumed constitutional conference of 1954 in Lagos, Awolowo's Action Group vehemently argued for a constitutional provision for the right of any of the federating regions to secede from the federation. This was opposed by Nnamdi Azikiwe's (first president of Nigeria) National Council of Nigeria and the Cameroons (NCNC). The conference ended with an agreement that no secession clause would be allowed in the amended constitution.

The first call for secession from the eastern part of Nigeria came from the then Premier of the region, Michael Okpara, who openly threatened to cause a secession of the Eastern region from Nigeria as a result of the circumstances surrounding the federal elections of December 1964. The following year, after the Western regional elections where it was alleged that the NCNC was massively rigged out, calls for the secession of the Eastern region became more strident, especially from some of the party's members in the Federal House of Representatives.

There were other pockets of secessionist agitations in the Middle Belt region principally by the Tiv ethnic group, and another in the present Niger Delta spearheaded by Isaac Boro and his two other compatriots. Boro and his Niger Delta Volunteer Force declared the Niger Delta Republic as Independent State on February 23, 1966, and gallantly engaged the federal forces in a battle that lasted for only twelve days (Awofeso, 2017). That was the first-ever real attempt by any group to attempt secession from Nigeria. They were eventually arrested, tried and sentenced to death for treason. In 1967 however, the then Head of State, Yakubu Gowon, exercised in their favour the prerogative of mercy, after repeated calls for clemency by the public.

The main secessionist bid that rocked the entire federation came in 1967 when the Eastern region, under the leadership of Lt. Col. Emeka Odumegwu Ojukwu, launched a massive attempt to break away from Nigeria. Before then, there was the counter-coup of July 1966 which was spearheaded by northern military elements, to retaliate the earlier 'Igbo' coup of January 1966, in which several military and political leaders of northern extraction were killed. The first coup was led by five Majors who were mostly Igbo. In the coup, foremost northern political leaders: Prime Minister Tafawa Balewa and the region's Premier, Sir Ahmadu Bello were killed. Also killed were four senior northern military officers and the Premier of the Western region (Ojibara, 2016). Sparing the President, Dr Nnamdi Azikiwe and the Premier of the Eastern region, Dr Michael Okpara, accentuated the impression that the coup was targeted at the north. This impression was reinforced by the inability of General Aguiyi-Ironsi, an Igbo who took over the mantle of leadership after the coup failed, to bring the coup plotters to justice (Duruji, 2012). The counter-coup and the pogrom that followed saw the massive massacre of Igbos residing in the north.

These sad events encouraged Igbos to believe that they were unwanted persons in other

parts of the country and those who survived the pogrom, returned home in droves, thereby widening the crack in national unity. Accounts of efforts made to resolve this crisis by the government at the centre led by Yakubu Gowon, and the Eastern regional government led by Ojukwu, have been well documented in extant literature. Suffice it to say that all efforts at peace-building at the time did not yield the desired results as the Governor of the Eastern region was left with no option than to declare the region as a sovereign state named the Republic of Biafra on May 29, 1967. Thus began the 30 months' fratricidal war that only ended in January 1970. Achebe (2012), Ademoyega (1981), Madiebo (1980), Forsyth (1977), and other authors have all presented comprehensive post-mortem accounts of the events of the war. The civil war and the victory for the Nigerian forces seemed to have put an end to secession attempts. Nonetheless, since the war ended, the feeling of injustice, marginalization and persecution have persisted among the Igbos (Ezemenaka & Prouza, 2016; Awofeso, 2017).

Because the fundamental issues for which the Igbos went to war in the first place were not addressed in the interregnum, agitations for Biafra have resurfaced, albeit with much vigour. Groups agitating for a revival of Biafra reappeared shortly after the return to democracy in 1999, alongside other ethno-nationalist movements across Nigeria. MASSOB was the strongest of this early generation of ethno-nationalist groups (Owen, 2016). The organization aimed to use a non-violent strategy to actualize the separation of Biafra from Nigeria. Its foot-soldiers were frequently having confrontations with the Nigerian security agencies which led to their arrests, trials, convictions and acquittals. Its leader, Ralph Uwazuruike, was on several occasions arrested and released. MASSOB under Uwazuruike, however, did not have a mass appeal. As a result, the coming into existence of indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) with mass appeal and huge membership revolutionized the agitation for a sovereign state of Biafra. The group was formed and led by Nnamdi Kanu. The commencement of the activities of the group coincided with the inauguration of Muhammadu Buhari as Nigeria's President. His administration sadly has not taken a conscious and deliberate step to address the concerns and agitations of the Igbos. We proceed now to examine the Biafra separatist agitations.

Biafra Agitations and the Crisis of Nation-Building

Igbo responses to alleged marginalization and victimization have historically taken different dimensions. So also is their quest for separate statehood. While an epoch was characterized by mere threats of secession, some others witnessed an actual attempt at secession either through violent means or recently, non-violent strategy. Ibeanu et al. (2016) have argued:

...the Igbo elites have historically responded to the perceived victimization of the group in two principal ways: by advocating for either more inclusion or separation. The inclusivist approach represents the attitude of the Igbo elite who see greater political, economic and social inclusion of the group as the most effective way of addressing the group's victimization. By contrast, radical-separatists hold that a sovereign, independent state of Biafra is the only solution to the victimization of the Igbo. While separatists agree on secession as the only solution to Igbo victimization, they differ on how this is to be achieved. They propound three possible routes to sovereignty namely, armed secession, civil disobedience and more lately, referendum.

Thus, when in 1964 the Premier of the Eastern region, Michael Okpara warned that his region would secede because of the circumstances surrounding the general elections of that year, it was a mere threat that was not backed with action. However, it was not the case three years later, when the people of the region were faced with genocide in other parts of the country. The Biafra that existed between 1967 and 1970 was created through a violent approach since that seemed the only option left after all efforts to resolve the crisis yielded no results. Hence, for thirty months, it was a full-blown war between separatist Biafra and the federal government.

In 1999 when MASSOB brought back the idea of Biafra into the consciousness of the Igbos, the organization made it clear that it tended to achieve the restoration of the Biafran state not through the war with Nigeria, but non-violent means. It therefore employed strategies such as organizing peaceful marches and protests, raising Biafran flags in public places, organizing sports competitions, and issuing its currency and passports to contest the writ of the Nigerian state. Despite the numerous clampdowns on its members by the Nigerian security forces, the group continued to preach non-violence as a strategy for actualizing its independence from Nigeria.

IPOB took a slightly different approach. Like MASSOB, it continuously preached non-violence even in the face of extreme provocation from the Nigerian security forces. However, its members have occasionally tended to be violent, especially while enforcing instructions from their leader, Nnamdi Kanu. According to Awofeso (2017), while the MASSOB claimed to be peaceful and non-violent in its approach, the IPOB tend using a violent approach. An example can be seen when the group invaded the Enugu State Broadcasting Service (ESBS) and when it attempted to gain entrance into Enugu State House of Assembly to hoist their flag on 5th June 2014.

Another important approach adopted by IPOB is the use of media propaganda. It understood the power of communication and therefore, established an underground radio station - Radio Biafra - from where it disseminated information to the supporters of their cause while using the same platform to cast aspersions on the Nigerian government and its leaders. This radio organization represents the most high-profile and radical of several diaspora-based movements in alliance with street-based groups (Owen, 2016). Thus, before long, Igbo youths across the globe got conscientized and keyed into the philosophy of Biafra. IPOB has also called for a referendum among the Igbo-speaking states to determine the choice of the people: whether to remain in Nigeria or to form a separate and independent State of Biafra. The Nigerian government would have none of this. At several fora, it has re-stated its resolve to keep the country united and indivisible. Apart from the arrest and continued detention of some of its leaders, it has also met the agitators with brutal force, using the security agencies to not only disrupt their rallies but also to shoot them. In the process, many have been killed and many more got maimed. This has attracted the attention of the international community as well, as some interested parties are beginning to question the human rights implications of the government's response.

Implication of the Clamour for Secession in the South-East on Nigeria

These agitations, no doubt, have socio-economic and political implications both on the southeast region and on Nigeria generally. In the first place, during the numerous demonstrations and protests by the IPOB, economic activities around the towns where these protests are held are disrupted. In fact, in the recent sit-at-home protest ordered by IPOB leader, Nnamdi Kanu, on 30th May 2017, economic and social activities in the entire

southeastern states and some south-south states were completely grounded. This has enormous implications on the economic development of the region, considering the number of man-hours lost to the protest on that day alone.

Security-wise, Ibeanu et al. (2016) have argued that the recurring agitation for Biafra has specific regional and national security implications, including the chances that mobilization of potential protesters could escalate armed violence and worsen the existing levels of insecurity. It could also lead to organized attacks on the people of the southeast residing in the north. The quit notice issued to the Igbos residing in the north in the recent past by a coalition of Arewa youths to leave the north by October 1, 2017, is in response to the activities of IPOB. Though the quit notice was later suspended, it is an indication of how far-reaching the consequences of the agitation could be.

Related to the above is the loss of lives and property that has always accompanied every clash of the agitators with security forces. On several occasions, security agencies have responded to the Biafran challenge with a brutal display of force, causing casualties in its wake. A lot of Biafran supporters have been killed during demonstrations. More have been injured, and properties of residents destroyed.

The resurgent Biafra separatist agitations have also caused severe strain on efforts at peace-building, national integration and political stability in Nigeria, thereby rolling back the little gains achieved since after the war. Agitations for Biafra are having snowball effects on other ethnic nationalities such as the Yoruba and the Niger Delta peoples as some elements amongst them are already agitating for Oduduwa and Niger Delta republics. In other words, it has awakened the consciousness of other radical elements in other parts of the country, especially groups that feel disadvantaged in the Nigerian project, to begin to question the rationale for their continued coexistence with the rest of Nigeria.

On a positive note, the agitations have sent a signal to the Nigerian authorities that unless an urgent tinkering is done to the Nigerian project, dismemberment might be a possible outcome. Aside from the core Hausa/Fulani north (except for few dissenting voices like those of Atiku Abubakar), every other part of the country is seriously calling for the restructuring of the country, even though there has not been a well-articulated proposal to that effect. This is positive fallout of the Biafran agitations for self-determination, as many believe that it is the current structure, nature and character of Nigeria that simmered and festered the secessionist agitations in the first place and that a restructured Nigeria will put the agitations to rest. In September 2017, several Yoruba organizations, political and religious leaders, as well as traditional rulers assembled in Ibadan to deliberate on the state of the union. The outcome of the summit was a call for urgent restructuring of the country or immediate dismemberment. Many other ethnic nationalities have made the same call, including the OhanezeNdigbo.

Response(S) of the Nigerian Government to the Secessionist Agitations in the South-East

How best can the agitations for a sovereign state of Biafra be contained? The Nigerian state has taken the option of use of force. From all indications, the use of force is not yielding the desired results, as the more force is applied, the more resolute the agitators become. According to Adibe (2017), the typical response of the Nigerian government over the years to separatist agitations is to brand the agitators "troublemakers," and send law enforcement agencies to use force to quell their agitations. This often results in casualties, stoking ethnic tensions in the process, which further hardens separatist agitations.

II. Theoretical Framework

The study adopted the Human Needs Theory (HNT) by John Burton in 1990. The major Assumption of this theory is that when an individual or group is denied his/their fundamental needs for identity, security, recognition or equal participation within a society, conflict is inevitable. Burton is quoted as saying:

We believe that the human participants in conflict situations are compulsively struggling in their respective institutional environments at all social levels to satisfy primordial and universal needs - needs such as security, identity, recognition, and development. They strive increasingly to gain the control of their environment that is necessary to ensure the satisfaction of these needs. This struggle cannot be curbed; it is primordial (Burton,1990:8).

This theory is based on the hypothesis that humans have basic needs that have to be met to maintain stable societies. Burton (1991) is further quoted below.

Now we know that there are fundamental universal values or human needs that must be met if societies are to be stable. That this provides a non-ideological basis for the establishment of institutions and policies. Unless identity needs are met in multi-ethnic societies, unless in every social system there is distributive justice, a sense of control and prospects for the pursuit of all other human societal developmental needs, instability and conflict are inevitable.

Burton suggests that there is a need for a paradigm shift from power politics to the 'reality of individual power'. In other words, individuals, as members of their identity groups, will strive to achieve their needs within their environment and if prevented from doing so, then conflict is inevitable.

This theory summarises that it advocates for the recognition and legitimization of the different values, inclinations and needs inherent in a society (ethnic, religious, cultural needs etc.) as necessary for a stable society. The needs must be satisfied holistically and not segmentally; i.e. not at the expense of the other. Doing so according to this theory will move conflict from zero-sum to win-win.

In a diverse ethnic/religious society like Nigeria, one cannot rule out ethnic/religious fanaticism inherent in her polity. This inadvertently affects the spread of developmental policies and nation-building, which has resulted evidently in sections of the country feeling excluded and marginalized; hence the call for secession in some quarters. If the assumptions of this theory are correct and juxtaposing them to the self-determination quest in the south-east, the theory becomes useful to the extent that it would help us understand the undertones of IPOB's agitations and guide us towards finding a lasting solution to these agitations in the south-east and Nigeria as a whole.

One of such solutions would be the ability of the federal government to promote an all-inclusive government and create an enabling environment where all agitations in the various regions of the country can be functionally addressed without bias or ethnic/religious inclination. This would give a sense of belonging to the regions and give them the hope of actualizing their

dreams and aspirations under the Nigeria umbrella.

III. Methodology

The study adopted the export-factor research design. This type of design is a quasi-experimental design which allows the researcher to look back in time for plausible causal factors of events without the interference of the variables in question. Another research design adopted for the study is the descriptive survey. The descriptive research design is a scientific method that involves observing and describing the behaviour of the subject without influencing the same in any way.

In applying ex-post-factor research design in the analysis of this study, the researcher observed dispassionately the different shades and phases of the conflict in the southeast region of Nigeria and employed the use of questionnaires and semi-structured interviews administered to 500 respondents to discover what culminated in the conflict. Since the actors of study are human beings and not matters or scientific elements, the possibility of influencing the behaviour of these people or characters does not exist.

The population of the study is comprised of 5,524,753 males and 5,426,018 million females. The total study population of the region, therefore, is 10,950,771 million people extracted from three states: Abia, Anambra and Imo States (National Bureau of Statistics, 2016).

Table 7
The Population of the Study

State	State Capital	Male	Female	Total
Abia	Umuahia	1,430,298	1,415,082	2,845,380
Anambra	Awka	2,117,984	2,059,844	4,177,828
Imo	Owerri	1,976,471	1,951,092	3,927,563
Total	3	5,524,753	5,426,018	10,950,771

Source: National Bureau of Statistics (2016)

The sample size of this study is 500 participants. The study adopted a purposive and accidental sampling procedure. The study purposively selected three states of Abia, Imo and Anambra out of the five states in the south-east from where we derived our study population. These states were selected due to the increasing activities of IPOB in the states. The sample size of 500 respondents was accidentally selected. Accidental sampling is a type of non-probability sampling in which the population of the study is easily accessible to the researcher. This method was chosen because the sample population all share similar characteristics and experiences regarding the secessionist agitations in the South-east and fall within the age bracket of 18 and above. The questionnaire was administered titled: "Self-Determination and Secession among the Indigenous People of South-East Questionnaire" and structured into four (4) sections. Respondents were asked questions related to age, gender, marital status, educational background, and occupation. There were also semi-structured interviews with respondents with the primary goal of obtaining information related to the study objectives. The study adopted descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentages, mean, standard deviation and bar charts in analyzing the research questions and Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to analyze the hypotheses.

Data Presentation and Analysis

The analysis of the distributed and retrieved questionnaires indicated that out of the 500 questionnaires distributed, 450 were successfully retrieved which made up 90% of the total

distributed questionnaires. This percentage was seen to be above average and suitable for analysis.

Evaluation of Research Questions

Research Question 1: What are the political, ethnic and socio-economic reasons for the movement for self-determination and secession in south-east Nigeria?

Table 1

The Causes of Self-Determination and Secession Movement in the South-East

S/N	Item	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1	The south-east was politically marginalized in federal appointments	3.17	0.73	Accepted
2	The south-east was economically marginalized	3.19	0.78	Accepted
3	Poor attention to infrastructural development in the south-east region	3.09	0.86	Accepted
4	The inability of the Nigerian state to resolve the grievances of the Igbo people	3.34	0.65	Accepted
5	Crisis of nation-building and underdevelopment	3.32	0.62	Accepted
Cluster Mean		3.24	0.71	Accepted

Source: Fieldwork Survey (2021)

Research Question 2: What are the impacts of the movement for self-determination and secession on peace and stability in Nigeria?

Table 2

The Impact of Movement for Self-Determination and Secession in the South-East

S/N	Item	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
7	Non-support of election in Nigeria	3.24	0.70	Accepted
8	Promoting non-participation in Nigerian politics	3.14	0.80	Accepted
10	Discouragement of external investors	3.40	0.71	Accepted
12	Disturbance of public peace	3.17	0.73	Accepted
Cluster Mean		3.19	0.72	Accepted

Source: Fieldwork Survey (2021)

Again, the study analysed the impact of the movement for self-determination and secession in the South-East region and Nigeria at large. The study discovered that the movement has caused political apathy especially in the area of federal elections in Nigeria (3.24 mean rate), and has attracted both internal and external condemnation towards the Nigerian government. Also, the study established that the movement has discouraged external investors from investing in Nigeria, and led to the disturbance of public peace across Nigeria. The cluster mean of 3.19 indicates a high agreement that the movement for self-determination and secession in the

southeast has caused numerous and negative setbacks to the region and the country at large.

IV. Discussion of Findings

Opinions on the reasons for the movement for secession in the southeast were gathered from respondents. The findings in figure 1 indicate that a large percentage of the respondents agree that the region has been marginalized in terms of economic distribution of the national wealth by the federal government with a mean rate of 3.19. They also claim political marginalization in terms of federal appointments and in the area infrastructural development with a mean rate of 3.17 and 3.09 respectively. Most of the respondents also agreed that the inability of the federal government to address the Igbo grievances constitute some of the issues causing the uprising in the region as well as ethnic differences in the country which has hindered nation-building.

Drawing from the above, it may be safe to say that the activities of the Indigenous Peoples of Biafra (IPOB) in recent times indicate the majority sentiments of the Southeast people towards the federal government.

The impact of recent agitations in the southeast (depicted in Table 2) was also analysed in this study. The data analysis reveals that the majority of respondents agree that the spate of agitations in the region has affected political and economic activities in the region. For example, campaigners for secession continuously discourage people of the region from participating in Nigerian political activities. The secessionist movement has also created a volatile environment which has discouraged investors from investing in Nigeria and worsened the already fragile peace in the region with the rise in conflict and armed confrontations with Nigerian security forces which have seen to the death of many including lives of security personnel as well as the destruction of private properties.

V. Conclusion

The recurring agitations for Biafra have serious implications for political stability and democratic consolidation in Nigeria. The prescription of IPOB as a terrorist group and the use of force to disperse agitators send a wrong signal to the people of the South-east that the federal government is unwilling to amicably address the lingering issues of the south-east people, thereby eroding the dwindling sense of belonging of the South-east people towards the Nigerian state. The effect of this is that it has increased ethnic sentiments and further divided the nation along ethnic lines.

The findings in this research reveal that the more agitations for self-determination and secession, the more political and economic instability persists in a nation. In other words, secessionist groups in Nigeria and the corresponding brutal response of the Nigerian government have simply heightened political instability in Nigeria.

There is no easy way to end the difficult situations posed by self-determination movements around the world presently. Clearly, in the face of the growing number of self-determination movements, there is a need to introduce a manageable and effective definition of the right to self-determination under International Law, though such a definition will not be easily arrived at and even then, it will most likely be inconclusive and equivocal; that notwithstanding, it will help shape the conditions under which groups within a sovereign territory can clamour for secession.

Recommendations

Given the above findings, this study recommends as follows:

1. *There is an urgent need to organize town hall meetings across the five states of the Southeast to ascertain the remote concerns and yearnings of the people. Doing so will give the impression that the Nigerian government is willing and responsive to address clamours from the region and give a sense of belonging to the Southeast people.*
2. *The government should refrain from the use of force to address secessionist agitations in the country, as doing so will only create a tense and volatile environment. For a democratic country like Nigeria, Diplomacy should be the watchword.*
3. *Marginalization was identified as a major push factor for the clamour for secession in the South-east; the federal government should enforce the federal character principle devoid of ethnic and religious sentiments in its administration. This will go a long way in reducing the ethnic and regional divide in Nigeria.*

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